

Disaster Preparedness: Utilizing a Checklist for Anesthetic management during a Massive Power Outage During Surgery

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Problem Statement

In the event of massive power outage (MPO) in the operating room (OR) intra-operatively, anesthesia providers are inadequately prepared to manage anesthesia delivery.

Purpose: Develop an evidence-based checklist to guide the anesthesia provider in the event of intra-operative MPO

Aims

- 1) Assess anesthesia provider perceived readiness for MPO management
- 2) Integrate MPO checklist into Kaiser Permanente (KP) OR crisis bundle

Background

“What’s the worst that could happen?”

- Increased risk of harm to patient
- Patient’s higher risk of awareness
- Restricted access to emergency medications and OR equipment

Project Design and Data Collection Tools

Setting: Southern California KP facilities

Sample: KP CRNAs employed at Southern California KP facilities

Data collection tool: Pre-implementation and MPO checklist evaluation survey

Data synthesis: Development of crisis checklist

Massive Power Outage Checklist

15 Massive Power Outage

Intraoperative power outage with or without backup generator

START

- 1 Call for help, obtain backup light source** (e.g. flashlight, cell phone, laryngoscope handle), Communicate with pharmacy to obtain anesthetic drugs and obtain Pyxis key. Ensure that all critical equipment is plugged into red outlets
- 2 Is the back up generator functioning?**
If not, go to step 3. If functioning, go to step 4
- 3 Power failure WITHOUT generator backup**
 - Check Anesthesia Gas Machine (AGM) function:
 - o If ventilator functional: maintain settings, use 100% FIO2
 - o If ventilator non-functional: switch to manual ventilation, use 100% FIO2
 - o Check O2 pipeline supply pressure; ventilate with Ambu bag using auxiliary O2 flowmeter
 - o If O2 pipeline supply pressure <36 psi, use O2 tank located behind AGM
 - Transition to TIVA due to loss of Waste Anesthesia Gas Disposal (refer to Propofol drip guide)
 - Assemble emergency drugs, additional anesthetics, and emergency equipment (refer to table)
 - o Pyxis cubic boxes can be opened with screwdriver, Matrix drawers with Pyxis key
 - Begin documenting on paper anesthesia record
 - Establish communication with anesthesia attending/float/manager
- 4 Power failure WITH generator backup**
 - Verify appropriate AGM settings
 - Check monitor, re-zero transducers if needed
 - Notify OR team
 - Ensure that data continues to populate into electronic medical record
 - Prepare for possible generator failure: assemble emergency equipment (refer to table)
- 5 Closed loop communication between anesthesia and surgery**
 - Discuss with surgical team whether to abort or continue procedure
 - Determine need and availability for higher level post-op care (e.g. ICU)

EMERGENCY EQUIPMENT

Portable light source (laryngoscope handle)
Airway adjuncts (ambu bag, mask, full O2 tank, ETT, LMA, OPANPA)
Monitoring equipment (sphygmomanometer, stethoscope, battery-powered transport monitor, colorimetric CO2 detector)
Supplies (gloves, syringes, needles, tape)
Emergency drugs (propofol, midazolam, opioid, neuromuscular blocker, phenylephrine, ephedrine, atropine, epinephrine, reversal drugs)

BATTERY LIFE OF MONITORING EQUIPMENT

BD Pyxis battery life is variable (access medications ASAP; flashing red lights indicate imminent power loss)
Aisys CS2 ~3.5 hrs
Phillips Intellivue ~3 hrs
Alaris IV infusion pump (2 channels) ~4.5 hrs
VBraun Perfusor IV infusion pump ~8 hrs
Full Oxygen E Cylinder ~2 hrs (at 5 L/min)

*How to calculate O2 E Cylinder Supply in Minutes:
(PSI O2 x 0.3)
(O2 L/min x 60)

PROPOFOL DRIP GUIDE (~100 mcg/kg/min)

Intermittent Syringe Bolus	Mini dripper (60 gtt/mL)
50 kg patient	50 kg patient
- 2.5 mL every 5 minutes	- 1 drop every other second
100 kg patient	100 kg patient
- 5 mL every 5 minutes	- 1 drop every second

PHYSICAL ASSESSMENT

- Determine HR
- Presence of pulses (no radial pulse = SBP <80 mmHg; no carotid pulse = SBP <70 mmHg; no femoral pulse = SBP <60 mmHg)
- Skin color
- Respiratory rate, work of breathing, adequate chest rise

Based on Yetter, A.G., Haman, R.J., Stamper, M.J., Twich, J.F., & Vacciano, C.A. (2019). Preparing for Total Power Failure in the Operating Room. *ANA Journal*, 87(4): 201-207. All reasonable precautions have been taken to verify the information contained in this publication. The responsibility for the interpretation and use of the materials lies with the reader.

Pre-implementation Survey

Q5 I believe a crisis checklist that includes the management of MPO would be a helpful cognitive tool.

Q8 During MPO, I can readily implement methods that do not require power to assess oxygenation, ventilation, and hemodynamics.

Q10 During MPO, with loss of AGM function and pyxis access, I am confident I can access anesthesia medications to convert to total intravenous anesthesia (TIVA).

MPO Evaluation Survey

Q2 Anesthesia providers at my facility will be more adequately prepared to manage a patient during massive power outage (MPO) with this checklist?

Q3 In the event of a MPO, I would utilize this MPO crisis checklist.

Q4 The MPO checklist is easy to read

Review of Literature

Anesthesia Provider Preparedness

- Patient management during intraoperative electrical failure remains a neglected topic in medical training and research (Ghanate and Kulkarni, 2016)

Incidence of MPO in the US:

Case Reports have described situations in which back up generators failed and resulted in MPO (Carpenter & Robinson, 2010)

The Joint Commission (TJC)

- TJC requires healthcare facilities to have contingency plans for disasters such as MPO (The Joint Commission, 2006)
- Facilities must identify vulnerabilities and adequately prepare for them (The Joint Commission, 2006).

Current Best Evidence

- Anesthesia providers must be prepared to monitor patients manually and have immediate access to emergency equipment (Eichhorn and Hessel (2010)
- Waste anesthesia gas disposal systems fail during MPO thus necessitating conversion to total intravenous anesthesia (Burgess & Anderson, 2019)
- Checklists have been an effective method in providing critical care during simulated or real-time crisis events in the OR (Acar et al., 2019)

Future Considerations

Adoption of MPO checklist into existing KP OR checklists

Creation of MPO reporting system

In-person training or simulations

MPO emergency tool kit